

The Influence of Work Culture on Employee Commitment at The Binjai City Regional Secretariat Office

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Abstract

The aim of this research is to determine and analyze the influence of Work Culture on Work Commitment at the Binjai City Regional Secretariat Office. This research was conducted using a causal associative quantitative approach. The sample used was all employees with ASN status with a total of 82 people taken using proportional sampling. The research results show that Work Culture has a positive and significant effect on Work Commitment. This is shown by the T-count value of T-count of 44.054 > t table 1.66412, with a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05. The regression coefficient shows that if Work Culture is increased by 1 unit, then Work Commitment will increase by 0.957 units assuming other variables remain constant. Apart from that, the results of the determination test show an Adjusted R Square value of 0.960 or 96.00%, which indicates that Work Culture has a very high influence on Work Commitment, while the remaining 4.00% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied. Thus, partially, Work Culture has a positive and significant effect on Work Commitment at the Binjai City Regional Secretariat Office. This identifies that improvements in Work Culture can contribute to increased Work Commitment

Keywords: Work Culture; Work Commitment

INTRODUCTION

Work culture includes the values and habits that are continuously implemented in an industry or organization. This is reflected in employee behavior, regulations, and interactions in the work environment. Work culture is crucial to industrial success because it impacts performance and collaboration. In everyday life, work culture also binds people in their interactions and behavior, both in family, organizational and business environments. This results in uniformity in actions and behavior. In an organizational context, work culture is a habit that is consistently carried out by employees. Although there are no strict sanctions for violations, these habits are considered norms that must be followed to achieve organizational goals.

This work culture creates a mindset that shapes efficiency and cooperation among organizational members (Mangkunegara, 2017). Work culture is basically a set of values that become a person's habits and influence the quality of their work (Pramudya et al., 2023). The values held by individuals in an organization can come from various sources such as customs, religion, norms and community rules. Individuals who practice good manners, religious observance and noble values tend to show good performance, characterized by a high work ethic, honesty and rejection of Corruption, Collusion and Nepotism (KKN) practices.

They are committed to continuously improving the quality of their work, which ultimately contributes significantly to the progress and success of the organization. These

values form the basis of a positive work culture, which encourages efficiency, cooperation and integrity in the work environment. According to Arachim, (2018). The work culture formed in an organization or industry has a significant influence on the level of employee work commitment. When the work culture values implemented by the organization are internalized by employees, they tend to feel more connected and dedicated to the organization. For example, if the work culture emphasizes collaboration, transparency, and a sense of responsibility, employees who adhere to these values will be more likely to feel engaged and committed to carrying out their duties. This statement is in line with the research results (Arachim, 2018) which states that there is a positive and very significant relationship between work culture and organizational commitment.

Based on initial observations made by the author through observations and interviews with the Head of the Binjai City Secretariat Office, several problems identified in the office are as follows, the first of which is that employees are less clear in understanding the concept of work culture that runs in the organization, resulting in unclear expectations and norms that must be followed by employees, as well as a lack of harmony in behavior and actions. Another problem that arises is the low level of employee commitment to work. Low work commitment can result in less than optimal performance, lack of loyalty to the organization, and lack of motivation to contribute optimally. Employee commitment is the level at which an employee identifies with the agency and its goals and is willing to maintain their participation in the agency. (Handoko, 2008). Employee commitment is encouraged by fair working environment conditions for workers, increasing employee respect, increasing employee commitment within the agency. While obeying (Robbins, Stephen P. and Mary Coulter, 2016). Employee commitment is the extent to which people adapt to a particular group and keep their members within the group.

In this research, the definition of employee commitment refers to Syahril's opinion (Syahril & Sulastrri, 2023) namely feelings of identification, loyalty and involvement shown by workers towards the organization or organizational unit. Commitment to an organization involves three attitudes, namely feelings of identification with organizational goals, feelings of involvement in organizational tasks, feelings of loyalty to the organization. Work commitment is something related to the meaning of organizational members towards their work and how employees carry out their duties within an organization. To measure the level of employee commitment in this research, indicators formulated by (Syahril & Sulastrri, 2023) that is :

- 1) Responsibility;
- 2) Loyalty
- 3) Involvement (participation in carrying out tasks);
- 4) Concern for work;
- 5) Feeling of identification.

To achieve this level of commitment, many factors can influence it. This research is limited to work culture factors which are moderated by the work environment. According to (Robbins, Stephen P. and Mary Coulter, 2016) Work culture is a system of shared understanding held by members of an organization that differentiates that organization from

other organizations. While obeying (Wibowo, 2013) Work culture is productivity, which is in the form of work behavior that is reflected in, among other things, hard work, tenacity, discipline, productivity, responsibility, motivation, benefits, creative, dynamic, consistent, consistent, responsive, independent, getting better, etc. In this research, the indicators of work culture refer to opinions (Wibowo, 2013) that is :

1. Professionalism means being competent in one's field and continuously developing oneself so as to produce the best performance and provide added value to the company.
2. Collaboration is building sincere and open relationships with all employees and all parties based on an attitude of mutual trust and respect to achieve common goals.
3. Excellent Service is providing service that exceeds customer expectations (internal and external).
4. Innovation is always developing new ideas and continuous improvements that add value to the company.
5. Exemplary is starting from yourself becoming a role model in behavior that reflects the work culture values of an organization or company

The aim of this research is to investigate the influence of work culture on employee commitment at the Binjai City Secretariat Office. It is hoped that the results of this research will provide a deeper understanding of the dynamics between work culture and employee commitment at the Binjai City Secretariat Office. It is hoped that the implications of this research can provide relevant recommendations for organizational management in increasing employee work commitment through managing work culture. The concept of this research is as depicted in the following conceptual framework image:

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

METHOD

This type of research is casual associative quantitative research with the aim of analyzing the pattern of relationships between variables with the aim of finding out the influence between two independent variables (exogenous) on the dependent variable (endogenous) (Kuncooro, Munajad, 2013). This research was carried out at the Binjai City Regional Secretariat Office. This research was carried out from May to June 2024. According to (Sugiyono, 2018) Population is a generalized area consisting of objects/subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics determined by researchers to be studied and then conclusions drawn. The population in this study is the entire number of employees at the City Regional Secretariat Office with a total of 105 employees with the following details:

Table 1. Total Population

No.	Part Name	Employee Status	Number of people)
1.	General Affair	ASN	17
		Honorary	107
2.	PBJ section	ASN	10
		Honorary	6
3.	Law part	ASN	8
		Honorary	5
4.	Welfare Section	ASN	6
		Honorary	8
5.	Prokopim Section	ASN	9
		Honorary	40
6.	Organization Section	ASN	9
		Honorary	3
7.	Government Section	ASN	8
		Honorary	7
8.	Economic Section	ASN	8
		Honorary	16
9	Development Administration Section	ASN	8
		Honorary	17
Amount		ASN	82
		Honorary	209
Total ASN + Honorary			292

Source: Binjai City Regional Secretariat Office

The sampling technique used in this research used a purposive sampling technique. According to (Sugiyono, 2019) Purposive sampling is a technique for determining samples with certain considerations. The reason for using this purposive sampling technique is because it is suitable for use in quantitative research, or research that does not carry out generalizations. Based on this theory, the number of samples in this research is the entire number of ASN employees, totaling 82 people. The data that will be used from this research is the data from the questionnaire distributed to respondents consisting of all employees in all divisions. The data analysis technique used in this research is a quantitative data analysis method using SPSS version 25.0.

Validity and reliability tests were carried out in order to test the quality of the research data. The validity test decision making criteria are as follows: If $r_{count} > r_{table}$, then the question item is valid. If $r_{count} < r_{table}$, then the question item is invalid. Meanwhile, the reliability test criteria are formulated if $r_{alpha} > r_{table}$ then the statement is reliable and if $r_{alpha} < r_{table}$ then the statement is not reliable. The linear regression model was formulated in this research with the following formula:

$$Y = a + bX$$

Where :

Y = Work Commitment

X = Work Culture

a = Constant

b = Regression coefficient

The t-test in this research was carried out to determine the significance of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable (Kuncooro, Munajad, 2013). According to (Kuncooro, Munajad, 2013) The determination test (R^2) is used to measure how much influence the independent variable has on the dependent variable. In other words, the coefficient of determination is used to assess the magnitude of the influence of the independent variable studied, namely Work Culture (X), on the dependent variable, namely Work Commitment (Y). The coefficient of determination (R^2) value ranges from zero to one ($0 < R^2 < 1$) which means, if $R^2 = 0$, then there is no influence between variable (X) and variable (Y). Conversely, if R^2 approaches 1, then the influence between variable (X) and variable (Y) becomes stronger. Testing of the coefficient of determination was carried out using SPSS version 25.0 software.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Results

Descriptive Analysis

Descriptive Analysis This test is used to determine the minimum and maximum scores, the highest score, the rating score and the standard deviation of each variable. The results are as follows:

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Work Culture	82	3.00	5.00	4.2317	.44050
Work Commitment	82	3.00	5.00	4.2463	.43010
Valid N (listwise)	82				

The table above shows that the measurement results show that respondents assess the Work Culture and Work Commitment at the Binjai City Regional Secretariat Office to be above average, with mean values of 4.2317 and 4.2463 respectively on a scale of 1-5. The variation in respondents' assessments of these two variables is high, with almost the same standard deviation (0.4405 for Work Culture and 0.4301 for Work Commitment), indicating that although there are individual differences in perception, the majority of respondents have quite positive views of these two variables.

b) Validity and Reliability Test Results

Validity Test Results

The validity test is used to measure whether a questionnaire is valid or not. Validity testing carried out in this research was through the Corrected Item-Total Correlation test or better known as Person Correlation.

Table 3. Validity Test Results for Work Culture Variables (X)

Variable	Correlation Value	Probability	Information
X1	0.948 > 0.2172	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
X2	0.916 > 0.2172	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
X3	0.742 > 0.2172	0.000 < 0.050	Valid

X4	0.875 > 0.2172	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
X5	0.797 > 0.2172	0.000 < 0.050	Valid

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25

From the data above it can be stated that the indicators for the Work Culture variable have a correlation coefficient value of > 0.2172 with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$ so it can be concluded that the indicators for the Work Culture variable are valid (Sugiyono, 2017).

Table 4. Validity Test Results of the Work Commitment Variable (Y)

Variable	Correlation Value	Probability	Information
Y.1	0.816 > 0.2172	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
Y.2	0.910 > 0.2172	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
Y.3	0.799 > 0.2172	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
Y.4	0.856 > 0.2172	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
Y.5	0.799 > 0.2172	0.000 < 0.050	Valid

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25

From the data above it can be stated that all indicators on the Work Commitment variable have a correlation coefficient value greater than 0.2172 with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$ so it can be concluded that the statements for the Work Commitment variable are valid (Sugiyono, 2016).

Reliability Test Results

According to (Ghozali, 2016) Reliability testing aims to measure how reliable or trustworthy the questionnaire distributed to respondents is, which is useful as an instrument in this research. The reliability measurement method used in this research is by looking at the Cronbach Alpha (a) value. The questionnaire is declared reliable if the Cronbach Alpha (a) value is > 0.61 .

Table 5. Reliability Test Results

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Work Culture	0.905	5
Work Commitment	0.890	5

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25.0

Based on table 5, it is known that the Cronbach Alpha (a) value of the Work Culture and Work Commitment variables is greater than 0.60. So it can be concluded that all indicators in the variable instrument are declared reliable or reliable so that they can proceed to research hypothesis testing

Quantitative Analysis

This analysis is intended to determine the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable. The test results are as follows:

Simple Linear Regression Analysis

This regression test is intended to determine changes in the dependent variable if the independent variable experiences changes. The test results are as follows:

Table 6. Simple Linear Regression Test Results

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	,986	,462		2,134	,036
	Work Culture	,957	,022	,980	44,054	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Work Commitment

Based on the test results in table 8, the regression equation $Y = 0.986 + 0.957X$ is obtained. This equation is explained as follows: 1) A constant of 0.986 means that if there is no Work Culture, then there is a Work Commitment of 1.942 points. The Work Culture regression coefficient is 0.957, meaning that Work Culture influences an increase in Work Commitment of 0.957 for every 1 point increase.

Analysis of the Coefficient of Determination

To determine the magnitude of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable, a coefficient of determination analysis was carried out. The test results are as follows:

Table 7. Coefficient of Determination Test Results

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,980a	,960	,960	,43055

a. Predictors: (Constant), Work Culture

The test results in table 7 show an Adjusted R Square value of 0.960 or 96.00%, which means that Work Culture has a very high influence on Work Commitment, while the remaining 4.00% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied.

t Test Results (Hypothesis Test)

Hypothesis testing with the t test is used to determine whether or not there is an influence of the dependent variable on the independent variable with the following hypothesis formulation:

Ho: There is no influence of Work Culture on Work Commitment at the Binjai City Regional Secretariat Office

Ha: There is an influence of Work Culture on Work Commitment at the Binjai City Regional Secretariat Office

The following are the results of the hypothesis test as shown in the following table:

Table 8. Hypothesis Test Results

	Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	,986	,462		2,134	,036
	Work Culture	,957	,022	,980	44,054	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Work Commitment

Based on the test results in table 8, the calculated t value is 44.054 > t table 1.66412, with a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05, thus it can be stated that Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted or there is a positive and significant influence between Work Culture and Work Commitment at the Regional Secretariat Office Binjai City.

Discussion

From the results of data analysis, research findings showed that work culture has a positive effect on work commitment. These findings are supported by research results from (Meizary & Magdalena, 2024), (Ernizalina et al., 2021) which states that work culture has a positive and significant effect on work commitment. The implications of the findings that work culture has a positive influence on work commitment are very significant for organizations. This shows that efforts to build and strengthen a positive work culture will directly contribute to increasing employee work commitment. With higher work commitment, employees tend to be more motivated, loyal, and productive, which in turn improves the overall performance of the organization (Raharjo & Masahere, 2020).

These findings emphasize the importance of developing programs and policies that support a positive work culture. Management must invest in training and development, create a work environment that is inclusive and values each individual's contribution, and ensure that the organization's values are reflected in every aspect of operations (Tahir & Iskandar Aulia, 2024). The results of this research also provide the basis for more effective human resource management policies, with a focus on creating and maintaining a supportive work culture. This will not only increase work commitment but also help the organization in achieving its long-term goals more efficiently and effectively (Sartika, 2024).

CLOSING

Conclusion

From the results of the research data analysis and discussion described above, it can be concluded that:

1. Hypothesis test results show that work culture has a positive and significant effect on work commitment. This can be seen from the T-count value of 44.054 > t table 1.66412, with a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05. This regression coefficient shows that if Work Culture is increased by 1 unit, then the change in Work Commitment as seen from the Y value will increase by 0.957 units assuming other variables are considered constant. Thus, partially Work Culture

has a positive and significant effect on employee job satisfaction at the Binjai City Regional Secretariat Office

2. Based on the results of the termination test, it shows that the Adjusted R Square value is 0.960 or 96.00%, which means that Work Culture has a very high influence on Work Commitment, while the remaining 4.00% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied.

Suggestions

Based on the research results, discussions and conclusions that have been explained, here are several suggestions that can be given to institutions, especially to the Binjai City Regional Secretariat Office:

1. Institutions need to continue to strengthen a positive work culture by developing values, norms and behaviors that encourage employee engagement and loyalty. Training and development programs that focus on building a work culture that is inclusive, collaborative, and values individual contributions are critical to increasing employee commitment.
2. Institutions must ensure that the work environment supports employee well-being. This includes providing support from superiors, providing career development opportunities, and ensuring balance between work and personal life. By creating a positive work environment, organizations can increase employee motivation and commitment.

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